

Entrepreneurship Education as a Predictor of Managerial Skills and Financial Skills Acquisition among Business Education Students in Delta State Tertiary Institutions

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ABSTRACT

Entrepreneurship education as a predictor of managerial skills and financial skills acquisition among Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions was examined in this study. Two research questions were answered and two null hypotheses were analyzed in the study. The study adopted the correlational research design. The population consisted of 1271 Business Education students in five tertiary institutions in Delta State. A sample of 304 students was used for the study. The sampling technique adopted was the simple random sampling technique. The research instrument was made of two parts –A and B. Part A consisted of respondents' personal data while Part B consisted of two subscales dealing with the research questions. The instrument was content and face validated. Cronbach Coefficient Alpha was used in testing the reliability of the instrument which yielded a coefficient of 0.97 for managerial skills Scale and 0.96 for financial skills Scale. and 0.717 for Entrepreneurship Education Scale. The Pearson Product Moment Correlation and Coefficient of Determination were used in answering the research questions. Regression analysis was used in testing the stated hypotheses. Based on the analysis, it was revealed that: Entrepreneurship education was a positive predictor of managerial skills and financial skills acquisition among Business Education students. It was recommended that sustained funding of entrepreneurship education in tertiary institutions, including business education programme, should be improved and proper consideration given for proper curriculum implementation in the annual budget by the Government.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship Education, Managerial Skills, Financial Skills & Business Education

INTRODUCTION

Education generally, is a social process that helps to maintain a dynamic society since the creation of mankind. It is the process involved in teaching, training and learning. Entrepreneurial education, therefore is seen as an instrument for change and development, a catalyst for a nations' socioeconomic progress, preparing individuals to flourish in a changing society and actively contribute to its evolution and advancement (Nwoye, 2013; Nwaham, 2010). The official education system is divided into three levels: primary, secondary, and postsecondary. Colleges of education, polytechnics, and universities are among the major postsecondary institutions in Nigeria, with the critical responsibility of creating skilled and high-level personnel to sustain the economy. It is expected that these institutions will align their efforts in order to generate graduates with significant societal and economic impact.

These graduates should be able to make use of their knowledge and skills acquired to alter and shape the environment while creating jobs to empower others. The realization of the above responsibility places entrepreneurship education at the center, and the rationale behind the objectives is linked to the inability of graduates to stand on their own and be self-employed after school. This could also be seen in the high rate of unemployment among tertiary institution graduates. Unemployment and unemployable graduates have become a serious challenge to tertiary institution educators and the Nigerian government (Aladejebi, 2018). The situation is tragic, with many young people who should be actively contributing to society finding themselves in the regrettable position of becoming beggars. They frequently move from one region to another within towns, states, and even across the country in pursuit of better

possibilities, despite the fact that they are ill-prepared and lack the requisite skills for the obstacles they face.

Some of the graduates have ventured into cybercrime and other vices which do not portray a good image of the country. According to Adegbenjo (2012), this occurrence signifies a waste of resources in the nation's personnel development. According to Adegbenjo, the kind of education required for self-employment and national progress has expanded to include broad reasoning, creative problem-solving, behavioural skills, and positive cognitive styles. In contrast to the earlier emphasis on narrow cognitive and occupational abilities better suited to specialised, directed work contexts, this new emphasis is on broad cognitive and occupational skills. This need explains why the Nigerian government stipulated in the national policy on education, the acquisition of appropriate skills, abilities and competencies; both mental and physical, as a pre-requisite for the individual to live in and contribute to the development of the society (Federal Republic of Nigeria, FRN, 2013).

According to Afolabi (2003), business education is a type of training that is primarily intended to prepare individuals for admission into a business career. Once in such a position, the goal is for them to be able to deliver effective services while also having the ability to move to higher levels of work. According to Udo and Babangida (2017), business education is a type of vocational education that teaches the skills, information, abilities, and attitudes required for productive employment in certain business occupations. According to Aliyu, as cited in Umezulike (2015), business education is the educational process focused on developing the skills, competencies, attitudes, and traits required for the economic system's efficiency.

Therefore, one of the major aims of a study in business education, per se, and education in general is to prepare students of such programmes for the world of work. This aim can be highly achievable when students acquire the relevant business education competency-based skills and competencies that will promote satisfaction brought about by successful self-employment and to enable them function well in the society. This satisfaction was brought about by the acquisition of entrepreneurial competencies such that the recipient will recognize the social and economic benefits accruing to the entrepreneur.

According to Emanuel, Dazala, and Daniel (2012), for a long time, educational institutions have prioritised generating graduates with minimal market value, while ignoring programmes like entrepreneurship that could contribute to employment development. The emphasis should change from merely finding employment to fostering graduates capable of being self-sufficient and creating jobs (Eugene, Adlive, & Agwubuike, 2013). There is an urgent need to encourage graduating students to think about options other than standard employment, such as starting their own enterprises. This move is especially important in the current work market, which provides little prospects for graduates of universities (Frazao, Santos, Oliveira, & Oliveira, 2010). According to Amidu, & Umaru, (2016), Teaching entrepreneurship in Polytechnic tertiary institutions without key learning facilities, infrastructures and manpower can best be described as cosmetic education.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study are outlined below:

- (1) To find out the relationship between entrepreneurship education and managerial skills acquisition among Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions

- (2) To find out the relationship between entrepreneurship education and financial skills acquisition among Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were raised and answered in this study:

- (3) What is the relationship between entrepreneurship education and managerial skills acquisition among Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions?
- (4) What is the relationship between entrepreneurship education and financial skills acquisition among Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions?

HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- (1) Entrepreneurship education is not a predictor of managerial skills acquisition among Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.
- (2) Entrepreneurship education is not a predictor of financial skills acquisition among Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Influence of Entrepreneurship Education on Managerial Skills Acquisition

Management is the process of getting things done through people. It is the process of harnessing the diverse resources (materials finance, people and time) in a manner as to achieve what the organization set to achieve. Nwachukwu (2018) defined management as the coordination of an organization's resources through the processes of planning, organising, directing, and controlling in order to achieve organisational objectives. Entrepreneurs can run successful businesses with the help of managerial skills. Heinz and Harold (2015) defined management as the art of creating and sustaining an environment in which individuals working in groups efficiently achieve specific goals.

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Management is generally viewed as a professional discipline that assembles and uses resources in terms of human, resources, financial resources, physical resources and time to accomplished objectives (Olowu, cited in Oluwasina, 2018), This implies that management involves the use of human resources through the means of planning, organizing and controlling of products in the industries in order to meet the customer requirements. It equally involves good planning, organizing, directing and controlling of workers and materials to effectively and efficiently meet set objectives of an enterprise (Oluwasina, 2018).

According to Etuk, as mentioned in Oluwasina (2018), management is the process of managing, administering, or overseeing a business's operations. It entails directing human efforts and resources, team-coordinating them, and providing critical leadership. Management, according to Isuwa (2015), is the process of organising, planning, and regulating all corporate activities, as well as directing people to ensure the efficient attainment of set goals. According to this point of viewpoint, management entails attaining an organization's goals through the coordinated performance of five distinct functions. According to Isuwa (2015), the classic management functions are as follows:

1. Planning or devising both short-range and long-range plans for the organization and setting goals to help achieve the plans
2. Organizing or deciding how to utilize human and material resources
3. Staffing, or hiring and training workers.
4. Directing, or guiding employees perform their work in such a manner that supports the organization's goals
5. Controlling or motivating the organization's progress towards reaching its goal.

Isuwa (2015) identified managerial incompetence as one of the specific reasons for business failure since managers do not have what it simply takes to run a small business. He emphasized that managerial skills of small business can be learned as managers are not born but made. He also claimed that valuable managerial abilities can be learned by trial and error, but that education can remove the majority of errors. Akinola (2016) also stated that one of the issues that entrepreneurs face is a lack of managerial abilities and expertise, and so urged that entrepreneurs receive adequate management training. Entrepreneurs, particularly those in

business-related fields, require managerial abilities because they also perform the role of managers because they are accountable for achieving their organization's goals and objectives. According to him, these skills are conceptual and technical skills. Conceptual skills are those skills required to relate parts of the company's work to the whole. Technical skills are those required for turning out the actual products or services of the firm and are needed for performing specific activities within the organization

Managerial skills are required by business related graduates in starting, developing and managing an enterprise. Management or managerial skills are skills required by the group who has responsibility to run an enterprise. According to Akinola (2016), managerial skills are skills required by an entrepreneur to formulate and execute policies of an enterprises which constitute management. Thus, Anyakoha (2019) stated some of the managerial skills to include; ability to communicate effectively, ability to make long and short term planning, ability to manage time, finance and meet job schedule.

Managerial skills are instrumental to entrepreneurial success. Okoli and Ezewanfor (2015) define managerial skills as the skills and abilities that improve the effective performance of management tasks, whereas Anumnu (2014) defines them as the ability to define goals and objectives, as well as plan and stimulate strategies to organise, motivate, direct, and control resources in order to achieve the desired goal(s). Management is also defined by Wale-Awe (2014) as a procedure of planning, organising, leading, and controlling organisational members' work as well as the utilisation of the organization's available resources to fulfil its stated objectives. Management involves the exhibition of different kinds of skills.

Some important management skills as identified by Anyakoha (2019) which are required by graduates for success in entrepreneurship also include the ability to or having knowledge of:

- a) Making long and short term planning;
- b) Purchase goods, tools and equipment;
- c) Factors involved in overhead control
- d) Inventory control and turnover
- e) Acquisition of management and supervisory skills
- f) Manage time and meet job schedules;

- g) Need for employees growth and development;
- h) Identify opportunities and generate ideas suitable to the opportunities; and
- i) Confidence to make a decision and acting upon them

Potential entrepreneur needs to possess management skills in order to achieve organization goals.

Lidimma (2021) identified management skills as follows:

1. Oversee organizational matters
2. Foster relationship among members of the organization
3. Evaluate all activities/operations in the process of goal attainment
4. Appraise employees' performance
5. Set a channel for effective feedback from customers
6. Purchase goods, tools and equipment
7. Produce demanded items before collection date
8. Manage time and meet job schedule
9. Be sensitive to the feeling of others
10. Handle difficult customers with patience and care
11. Develop, interpret and implement organization policies
12. Set attainable goals for the organization
13. Create long term vision for the organization
14. Create an open door policy
15. Control, directs and delegate authority
16. Organized human/material resources for goals attainment
17. Maintain authority in dispensation of leadership
18. Have knowledge of need for employee growth and development
19. Evaluate the impact of personnel in the organization

Evidently, management skills are essentially required by business education graduates to effectively achieve entrepreneurial goals through coordinated efforts of planning, organizing, staffing, directing and controlling. It is with this understanding that Ejeka and Mgbonyebi (2016) asserted that graduates of entrepreneurship programme need to develop management skills in order to know how to take care of men and materials under their care. These men and materials

are scarce or insufficient and need to be managed optimally. Some entrepreneurs regard human beings as machines but those who have managerial skills apply the principles of human relations in treating their workers

Entrepreneurship Education as a Predictor of Financial Skills Acquisition

Financial literacy is very important for entrepreneurs because of the knowledge of budget management, procedures, credit management, and even the financial risks of business operations. Financial skills or accounting skills is regarded as an area of study needed to equip recipients with knowledge, skills and attitude necessary for efficient financial calculation required for occupational competence, and economic activities of the organization. These are measured, recorded and communicated to interested parties for analysis and interpretation. This is rooted on the need to keep the records of business transactions. Both Umunnah (2022) and Ahukannah, Ndinechi and Arukwe (2019) holds the premise that the accounting activities role in operating a business enterprise are the recording of financial data, analyzing financial data, preparation of accounting statements and communicating financial information to employers.

Accounting and financial skills needs of entrepreneurship education students for effective economic survival include: Knowledge of accounts; Knowledge of costing; competency in interpreting financial statement; ability to acquire the skill of preparing financial statements; ability to understand payroll and various deductions; ability to know gross and net profit; ability to know sources of funds; ability to know how to obtain loans; a knowledge of federal, state and local government levies, taxes and regulations; and to prepare simple budget (Akpotowoh & Amahi, 2016).

While record-keeping abilities may not be recognised as a good element, research suggest that financial management skills contribute positively to business success (Carland & Carland 2019; Akande 2021). Attention-directing abilities assist owners/managers in making critical production and price decisions, whereas reporting abilities entail the manner of disseminating company information to stakeholders. Entrepreneurs are expected to have financial management skills because it is primarily an accounting talent (Akande, 2021). Accounting, according to Oladejo (2018), is an information system that provides economic information to decision-makers, driving

corporate growth beyond mere record-keeping to making critical economic decisions for owners and stakeholders.

RESEARCH DESIGN

This study adopted the correlational research design. It entails the researchers going into the field to gather information without interfering with the natural setting. In this study, the researchers cannot manipulate events. In this type of study, according to Kumar (2005), the central premise is to establish the existence of an association between two or more aspects of a situation. By utilizing this research study, the researcher attempts to examine the previously-not-studied relationship between entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial skills acquisition. This design allows the researcher to analyse and interpret the existing situation or to answer questions and test hypothesis concerning the current status of the phenomena of interest using correlational statistics such as Pearson-r, linear regression and multiple regression among others.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The target population of the study consisted of all Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions. The population comprises of 1,520 students from five tertiary institutions in Delta State

Table 1: Population of Business Education Students according to tertiary institutions in Delta State

NO	Higher Institution	Population
1	Delta State University, Abraka	399
2	Federal College of Education, Technical, Asaba	340
3	University of Delta, Agbor	223
4	College of Education, Warri	320
5	College of Education, Mossogar	238
		1,520

Source: Various Departments of Business Education in Delta State Tertiary Institutions

SAMPLE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

All the population for this study cannot be reached due to the large number involved; hence 304 students representing 20% of the population was used as sample for the study. The percentage for the sample size is in line with the suggestions of Nworgu (2006) that for descriptive research a sample of 10% of the population is considered acceptable minimum for very large population. The simple random sampling technique was used in the selection of sample for the study.

RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

The instrument used in this study was a structured questionnaire titled “Entrepreneurship Education as Predictors of Managerial Skills and Financial Skills Acquisition Questionnaire” The instrument was made up of two Parts. Part A consisted of the demographic information of respondents such as gender and Age. While Part B comprised two sections designed to find out the views of students who were the respondents. Modified Four points Likert-scale of strongly agree (4 points), agree (3 points), disagree (2 points) and strongly disagree (1 point) were used to score the responses in the instrument. The researchers designed the questionnaire after a careful review of relevant literature based on the objectives of the study and the research questions.

The instrument was given to three lecturers in Business Education and Measurement and Evaluation: two lecturers in Business Education and one lecturer from Measurement and Evaluation to validate the instrument in order to examine the extent to which the statements prepared were appropriate for the purpose of the study. They made correction and redirected the contents of the instrument. The researcher effected the corrections based on the comments, suggestions and recommendations of the validators. Hence, the instrument was considered to have possessed face and content validity.

RELIABILITY OF INSTRUMENT

The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach – Alpha for determining the internal consistency of the items of the instrument. This was done by administering twenty (20) copies of the instrument to twenty students in the Ambrose Ali University, Edo State who were not part of the study area. The yielded reliability coefficient were 0.97 for managerial skills Scale and 0.96 for financial skills Scale.

METHOD OF DATA ANALYSIS

The Pearson product moment correlation and coefficient of determination were used in answering the research questions while F-test associated with regression analysis was used in testing the stated hypotheses at an alpha level of 0.05 level of significance. All statistical analysis was conducted using the SPSS statistical tool. The SPSS computation for answering and testing the hypotheses.

PRESENTATION OF RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Research Question One

What is the relationship between entrepreneurship education and managerial skills acquisition among Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions?

In answering the above research question, data collected from the respondents in relation to managerial skills acquisition were correlated with data generated from the entrepreneurial scale. Summary of the analysis is as shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Pearson-r and coefficient of determination on the relationship between entrepreneurship education and managerial skills acquisition among Business Education students

Variable	N	r	r²	r²%	Decision
Entrepreneurship Education	304	.161	.026	2.6	Positive Relationship
Managerial Skills Acquisition					

*Significance: $P \leq 0.05$

The result in Table 2 shows the Pearson product moment correlation coefficient (r) value of 0.161 as the positive relationship between entrepreneurship education and managerial skills acquisition among Business Education students. The coefficient of determination (r²) value of 0.126 and the level of relationship between entrepreneurship education and financial skills

acquisition was 12.6%. This implies that entrepreneurship education was good at predicting managerial skills acquisition among Business Education.

Research Question Two

What is the relationship between entrepreneurship education and financial skills acquisition among Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions?

To answer the above research question, data generated from the responses of students on the financial skills acquisition scale were correlated with data from the entrepreneurial education scale. Summary of the analysis is as shown in Table 3.

Table 3 Pearson-r and Coefficient of Determination on the relationship between entrepreneurship education and financial skills acquisition among Business Education students

Variable	N	r	r ²	r ² %	Decision
Entrepreneurship Education	304	.122	.115	1.5	Positive relationship
Financial Skills Acquisition					

*Significance: $P \leq 0.05$

The result in Table 3 shows the Pearson product moment correlation coefficient (r) value of 0.122 as the relationship between entrepreneurship education and financial skills acquisition among Business Education students. The coefficient of determination (r²) value of 0.115 and the level of relationship between entrepreneurship education and financial skills acquisition is 11.5%. This implies that entrepreneurship education was good at predicting financial skills acquisition.

Hypothesis 1:

Entrepreneurship education is not a predictor of managerial skills acquisition among Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.

In testing the above hypothesis, regression analysis was computed. Summary of the analysis is as shown in Table 4.

Table 4 Regression analysis on relationship between entrepreneurship education and managerial skills acquisition among Business Education students

ANOVA					
Model 1	SS	Df	MS	F	P
Regression	147.806	1	147.806	7.997	.005 ^b
Residual	5581.721	302	18.483		
Total	5729.526	303			

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		standardized Coefficient		P
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-Ratio	
(Constant)	29.427	2.500		11.773	.000
Entrepreneurship Education	.165	.058	.161	2.828	.005

Dependent variable: Managerial Skills Acquisition

Table 4 shows the F-calculated value of 7.997 and a p-value of 0.005. Testing the hypothesis at an alpha level of 0.05, the p-value of 0.005 is less than the alpha level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implies that, entrepreneurship education is a positive predictor of managerial skills acquisition among Business Education students.

The unstandardized coefficient (B-value) of 0.165 shows that entrepreneurship education is a good predictor of managerial skills acquisition among Business Education students. The B value of 0.165 shows that for every one unit change in entrepreneurship education, there will be a corresponding unit change in the level of managerial skills acquisition. The standardized coefficient value [$\beta = 0.161$; $P < 0.05$] indicates that entrepreneurship education was a significant predictor of managerial skills acquisition. This means that entrepreneurship education is significant at predicting managerial skills acquisition at P-value of 0.05.

Hypothesis 2:

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Entrepreneurship education is not a predictor of financial skills acquisition among Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions.

In testing the above hypothesis, regression analysis was computed. Summary of the analysis is as shown in Table Summary of the analysis is as shown in Table 5

Table 5: Multiple regression analysis on entrepreneurship education as a predictor of financial skills acquisition among Business Education students

ANOVA					
Model 1	SS	Df	MS	F	P
Regression	118.560	1	118.560	4.556	.034 ^b
Residual	7858.910	302	26.023		
Total	7977.470	303			

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		standardized Coefficient		
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t-Ratio	P
(Constant)	25.565	2.966		8.620	.000
Entrepreneurship Education	.148	.069	.122	2.134	.034

Dependent Variable: Financial Skills Acquisition

Table 5 shows the F-calculated value of 4.556 and a P-value 0.034. Testing the hypothesis at an alpha level of 0.05, the p-value of 0.034 is less than the alpha level of 0.05. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This implied that entrepreneurship education is a predictor of financial skills acquisition among Business Education students. The unstandardized coefficient (B) of predicting financial skills acquisition from entrepreneurship education was .148. The standardized coefficient or Beta value [$\beta = 0.122$; $P > 0.05$] indicates that entrepreneurship education was a significant predictor of financial skills acquisition; therefore, entrepreneurship education was significant at predicting financial skills acquisition at P-value of 0.05.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion findings for the study are in line with the answered research questions and the tested hypotheses.

Entrepreneurship Education as Predictor of Managerial Skills Acquisition

The analysis in Table 2 showed that there was relationship between entrepreneurship education and managerial skills acquisition among Business Education. This finding indicates that changes in managerial skill acquisition were attributed to entrepreneurship education. Table 4, which presented the corresponding hypothesis, revealed that “entrepreneurship education was a predictor of managerial skills acquisition”. This finding implies that managerial skills acquisition among students was predicted by entrepreneurship education. This finding is in line with Iradale (2022) and Ojo (2021). Iradale (2022) corroborating the above finding states that “a good graduate of entrepreneurship education would acquire enough managerial skills relevant to the management of small business and generate equipment opportunities for youths”. Hence, to him, “entrepreneurship education was a good predictor of managerial skills acquired by Business Education students”. Ojo (2021) in supporting the above finding also revealed in his study that entrepreneurship education equips “graduates with entrepreneurial and managerial skills to a great extent. Hence, a study of entrepreneurship education influences students’ managerial skill acquisition. As a result of being exposed to entrepreneurial training, students will develop innovative and creative abilities that will help them to be successful managers of businesses formed by them or when employed as a manager of a business.

Entrepreneurship Education as Predictor of Financial Skills Acquisition

The analysis in Table 3 which answered the second research question revealed that “entrepreneurship education was a good predictor of financial skills acquisition among Business Education students in Delta State tertiary institutions”. This analysis indicates that changes in financial skills acquisition could be attributed to entrepreneurship education. Further testing of hypothesis, as shown in Table 5 showed that “entrepreneurship education was a good predictor of financial skills acquisition”. This indicates that “entrepreneurship education was significant at predicting financial skills acquisition among students”. This finding is in line with Abdulkareem and Afolabi (2022) who pointed out that entrepreneurial education through social studies predicts the acquisition of financial management skills of students. In supporting the above finding Akande (2021) also pointed out that Business Education entrepreneurial education was a good predictor of financial management skill acquisition. Since financial management is an accounting

skill, owner/manager entrepreneurs are expected to possess such for vital business growth and development. Through Business Education entrepreneurial education, students will be taught financial management skills such as book keeping and record management skills in addition to many other financial skills that will enable them to be useful to small scale enterprise.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it was concluded that:

- (1) Entrepreneurship education significantly predicted managerial skills acquisition among Business Education students
- (2) Financial skills acquisition among Business Education students was predicted by entrepreneurship education.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are made for the study:

1. Private sector participation should be encouraged for them to have active and increased participation in funding entrepreneurship programmes.
2. The government should sufficiently empower Business Education graduates who may want to venture into small scale enterprise upon completion of their tertiary education and also mentor and monitor their activities to ensure their sustenance and active contribution to nation building is achieved.
3. Further attention should be given to tertiary institutions in the area of provision of facilities such as, instructional materials, classrooms, and information services for students and staff personnel. This will ensure that business education instructors or entrepreneurial instructors do their job of teaching while students do their job of learning to acquire the necessary entrepreneurship competencies necessary for the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills.

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